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**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ONLINE TAXI BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
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Date: 2022/03/10

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Our project entitled “**PREPAID TAXI MANAGEMENT SYSTEM SYSTEM**” aims is to book the taxis at all the fare charges. Manual system that is employed is extremely laborious and quite inadequate. It only makes the process more difficult and hard.

The aim of our project is to develop a system that is meant to partially computerize the work performed in the prepaid taxi management system like generating monthly daily bookings, record of routes available , fare charges of every route; store record of the customer.

We used Microsoft Visual Basic 6.0 as front end and MS-Access 2000 as back end for developing our project. Visual Basic is primarily a visual design environment. We can create a VB application by designing the form and that make up the user interface. Adding visual basic application code to the form and the objects such as buttons and text boxes on them and adding any required support code in additional modular.

Microsoft Access 2000 is a powerful relational database application with which a desktop user can efficiently create and manipulate database systems. Access targets the desktop category and works best for individuals and workgroup

Managing megabytes of data for multi-user access to the same database, Access uses file-server architecture, rather than client-server architecture.

Access is included in the professional and developer editions of Microsoft office.

The overall project report is divided into some parts. These parts are further divided into their subparts. In the parts we have described the purpose, scope of

the project, objective of the project i.e. approach which used for developing this software. It includes the topics like the problems with the existing system and the functionality of the organization. Introduction to tools, design, coding, testing and debugging of the system are discussed in very detail. We have also provided the names of the books from which we have taken guidance to complete the work. Last section contains the matter about the overall work performed and the efforts taken to complete the project.

1.2 INTRODUCTION OF THE TAXI MANAGEMENT SYSTEM:-

A **taxicab**, also **taxi** or **cab**, is a type of vehicle for hire with a driver, used by a single passenger or small group of passengers often for a non-shared ride. A taxicab conveys passengers between locations of their choice. In modes of public transport, the pick-up and drop-off locations are determined by the service provider, not by the passenger, although demand and share taxis provide a hybrid bus/taxi mode.

Taxicabs arrived in 1911 to complement horse wagons. There are 52000 – 55000 Number of taxicabs. According to Government of Nepal regulations, all taxicabs are required to have a fare-meter installed. However, enforcement by authorities is lax and many cabs operate either without fare-meter or with defunct ones. In such cases, fare is decided by bargaining between the customer and the driver. Taxicabs face stiff competition from auto rickshaws but in some cities. In Nepal, most taxicabs, especially those in Delhi and Mumbai, have distinctive black and yellow liveries with the bottom half painted black and upper half painted yellow. In Kolkata, most taxis are painted yellow with a blue strip in the middle.

SHARED TAXI CABS

In cities and localities where taxis are expensive or do not ply as per the government or municipal regulated fares, people use Share taxis. These are normal taxis which carry one or more passengers travelling to destinations either en route to the final destination, or nearby the final destination. The passengers are charged according to the number of people with different destinations. A similar system exists for auto rickshaws, known as Share autos.

As one example, "Shared taxis" - and known just as that – have been operating in Mumbai, Nepal, since the early 1970s. These are more like a point to point service that operates only during the peak hours. During off peak hours, they ply just like the regular taxis, can be hailed anywhere on the roads, and passengers are charged by the meter. But in order to bridge the gap between demand and supply, during peak hours, several of them operate as Shared Taxis, taking a full cab load of passengers to a more or less common destination. The pick-up points for these taxis are fixed, and are marked by a post that says, “Shared Taxis” and cabs line up at this point during peak hours. They display the general destination they are headed for on their windscreens, and passengers just get in and wait for the cab to fill up. As soon as this happens - which takes less than a couple of minutes - the cab moves off. Fares are a fixed amount – fixed between the Taxi Unions and the authorities for the point to point distance - and are far lower than the metered fare to the same destination, but higher than the bus or train fare. Time taken is obviously much less than that by bus. These taxis are very popular because of the lack of waiting time, faster journey speeds, greater comfort, and absence of the crush loads of peak hour commuter traffic in buses and trains.

Chapter 2 study structure

2.1 SCOPE OF THE PROJECT:-

The scope of project included evaluation of the application and was primarily concerned with the transaction related to booking of tickets from the terminal operated by the railway personnel.

2. Applications controls, stimulation and online enquiries were used to evaluate data validation and program logic. The selected data, as made available, for substantive checking of the completeness, integrity and consistency of data using computer assisted applications such as VB, MS-ACCESS and Structured Query Language(SQL).

3.The records maintained in the database of the Prepaid taxi management were also reviewed. Discussions were held with the database users to gain understanding regarding the various functional aspects of the system

2.2 objectives of the system

The firm handles all of the work manually, which is very tedious and mismanaged.

The objective of our project is as follows:

1. To keep the information of Customer.
2. To keep the information of number of bookings in current month.
3. To keep the detail of taxis route.
4. To keep the information of cancellation and modification of booking in current month.
5. To maintain the record of the every employee of every route .

Chapter 3 System Analysis

3.1 Identification Of Problem:

The old manual system was suffering from a series of drawbacks. Since whole of the system was to be maintained with hands the process of keeping, maintaining and retrieving the information was very tedious and lengthy. The records were never used to be in a systematic order. there used to be lots of difficulties in associating any particular transaction with a particular context. If any information was to be found it was required to go through the different registers, documents there would never exist anything like report generation. There would always be unnecessary consumption of time while entering records and retrieving records. One more problem was that it was very difficult to find errors while entering the records. Once the records were entered it was very difficult to update these records.

In present, work done in the railway board is performed manually which is a great headache for the department .The reason behind it is that there is lot of information to be maintained and have to be kept in mind while running the business .For this reason we have provided features Present system is partially automated (computerized), actually existing system is quite laborious as one has to enter same information at three different places.

Following points should be well considered-:

Documents and reports that must be provided by the new system: there can also be few reports, which can help management in decision-making and cost controlling, but since these reports do not get required attention, such kind of reports and information were also identified and given required attention.

Details of the information needed for each document and report.

The required frequency and distribution for each document.

Probable sources of information for each document and report.

With the implementation of computerized system, the task of keeping records in an organized manner will be solved. The greatest of all is the retrieval of information, which will be at the click of the mouse. So the proposed system helps in saving the time in different operations and making information flow easy giving valuable reports.

3.2 Feasibility Study:

Feasibility study is the phase in which the analyst checks that the candidate system is feasible for the organization or not. This entails identification, description & evaluation of the system. Feasibility study is done to select the best system that meets the performance requirement. If the feasibility study is to serve as a decision document, it must answer key questions.

- Is there a new and better way to do the job that will benefit the user?
- What are the costs and savings of the alternatives?
- What is recommended?

The most successful system projects are not necessarily the biggest or most visible in the business but rather those truly meet user's expectations.

Feasibility considerations

Three key considerations are involved in the feasibility study. They are as follows:-

Economic Feasibility:

Economic analysis is the most frequently used method for evaluating the effectiveness of the candidate system.

We analyze the candidate system (computerized system) is feasible as than the manual system because it saves the money, time and manpower. It also feasible according to cost benefits analysis.

Technical Feasibility:

Technical feasibility centers around the technology used. It means the candidate system is technically feasible i.e. it don't have any technical fault and work properly in the given environment. Our system is technically feasible; it is providing us required output.

Behavioral Feasibility:

Behavioral feasibility is the analysis of behavior of the candidate system. In this we analyze that the candidate system is working properly or not. If working than it communicating proper with the environment or not. All this matters are analyzed and a good candidate system is prepared. Due to the change of system what is the change in behavior of the users, this factors are also analyzed.

4. INTRODUCTION TO TOOLS:

4.1 Introduction of Visual Basic:

Over past few years visual basic 6.0 (front end) the relational data base management system has been fine-tuning it is offering a large complex application in the relational market. Visual basic 6.0 is a front end (i.e. uses graphical user interface) visual basic 6.0 uses windows environment. It may use any DBMS or RDBMS as a back-end through ODBC (open database connectivity).

For our purpose of development, in our project we used Visual Basic 6.0 because visual basic 6.0 has following outstanding features and qualities.

Advantages Of Visual Basic:

1. Visual Basic applications are event driven. Event driven means the user is in Control of the application.
2. Visual Basic supports the principle of object-oriented design.
3. Visual Basic is a complete window application development system.
4. Visual Basic is infinitely extensible through the use of active x controls dynamically linked libraries (dll's) and adds dins.

The Fast Track To Windows Development

Visual Basic is primarily a visual design environment. We can create a VB application by designing the form and that make up the user interface. Adding visual basic application code to the form and the objects such as buttons and text boxes on them and adding any required support code in additional modular.

Friendly Environment

Creating a form, adding controls to form and writing code behind the form are all managed within a friendly environment.

Graphical User Interface

Application developed in DOS environment has to include its own set of video, keyboard and printer drivers. In other words many DOS programs provided virtually no user interface at all. Since windows is preferable over DOS and Visual Basic is windows based hence millions of users can use applications with no documentation or training:

The graphical user interface provides a graphical environment to user as front-end for their operating system through graphical objects and therefore screen looks very attractive and almost has three-dimensional qualities. The point and shoot use of a GUI (Graphical User Interface) make use of the operating system and programming easy.

Visual basic 6.0 connect to number of back-end DBMS and RDBMS such as SQL, FoxPro, Sybase, Oracle etc.

Open Database Connectivity

Visual basic 6.0 connects to any back-end DBMS system whose DBMS cores follow the open database connectivity rules and this connectivity is established by open database connectivity.

The data storage may belong to any DBMS engine specifically supported by visual basic 6.0 driver or any DBMS that supported open database connectivity.

The data entry and validation screens are created in visual basic 6.0 connects with whichever engine is specified at the time of screen was created and manipulated data within that engine.

4.2 Client server computing and visual basic 6.0:

The client / server programming is also a distributed application processing and co-operating application processing. It has three distinct components, each focusing on specific job.

The three components are:

1. Client application
2. A Database Server
3. A network for connecting the first two components.

1. Client Application:

Client application (i.e. front end) is the part of the system that users employ to interact with data. The work of client is requesting and receiving information forms a database server (back-end). Client application can be developed rapidly using visual basic 6.0.

2. A Database Server:

A Database server focuses on efficiently managing resources such as the table in which data lies. The server's primary job is to manage the data tables optimally among multiple clients that concurrently request server for same resources. Visual basic can connect to a number of RDBMS that are in trend.

3. Network for connecting the first two components:

A network and communication software are the vehicle that transports the data between the clients and the server. The system both client and server run communication software that allow them to talk across a network.

4.3 Object Oriented Programming Approach:

The visual basic 6.0 uses the OOPS approach. In OOPS, a table is treated as also object and the data being attached to as user specified parameters the forms also treated as objects for this windows object for this window object. The firing of code shippers based on events occurring such as clicking on a button via a mouse.

Visual Basic Libraries:

When we create commercial application we create object such as windows, data windows, menus etc. these objects that you create using an appropriate visual basic pointer are stored in libraries files.

When application has to run visual basic there objects from their libraries and visual basic gives you a library painter to help you manage your libraries.

Events in Visual Basic:

Visual basic commercial applications are event driven. The user of the application Controls the flow of the application by the action they take.

Visual Basic's Debugging tool:

To distribute application created in visual basic we create an executable i.e. an exe file, also there is a distribution kit to distribute the application.

Features of Visual Basic:

1. Visual basic provides a GUI which and therefore screen looks very attractive.
2. Work on client / server computing model.
3. Object Oriented programming approach.

4. Visual basic provides several tool bars, which make working quick and easy.
5. It is front end and DBMS as a back end so it uses all the features of RDBMS like referential integrity foreign key etc.
6. It uses a micro help line, which visual basic uses to display starters to display information through the session.

Feel Of Windows Environment

Microsoft Windows environment is built-in to Visual Basic application. No need to work with any windows compatible hardware since windows provides drivers for thousand of different printer's video adapter, modems and other peripherals.

CHAPTER -5

5.1 Introduction of MS-Access

Over the past several years, relational database management system have become the most widely accepted way to manage data relational system often benefits such as:

1. Easy access to all data.
2. Flexibility in storage and modeling.
3. Reduced data storage and redundancy.
4. Independence of physical storage & logical data designs.
5. A high-level data manipulation language (SQL).
6. Tables & table operations are well defined because relational theory is founded in set theory, relational algebra & relational calculus.

Our of this the reason for introducing relational model is to increase the productivity of the application programmer by eliminating the need to change application programs when a change is made to the database.

As the technologies associated with RDBMS have grown rapidly in recent years, the appeal of relational databases has become apparent to a much wider audience.

The phenomenal growth of the relational technology has led to more demand for RDBMS in environments ranging from personal computer to large highly secure CPU with users ranging from very casual to very sophisticated.

Microsoft Access 2000 is a powerful relational database application with which a desktop user can efficiently create and manipulate database systems. Access targets the desktop category and works best for individuals and workgroup

Managing megabytes of data for multi-user access to the same database. Access uses File-server architecture, rather than client-server architecture.

Access is included in the professional and developer editions of Microsoft office.

As a leader in the desktop database category, Microsoft Access makes it easy for users to find and manage their data to make better business decision. With strong integration with Microsoft Office, Access offers a similar appearance and functionality to that found in the popular Microsoft word and Excel applications for general business users, Access provides easy to use wizards throughout, such as the database wizard for getting up and running quickly and the simple query wizards for easily finding information from the data. The combination of ease of use and power in access makes it the top choice among developers who frequently use Access as a front end in a client – server scenario.

The only problem with MS-ACCESS is that it cannot provide strong security features. But in front of its fast execution features this drawback can be neglected as the firm does not need any type of security whether it is operational, database, or any other security. But in application development some restriction are made of some places so that our database cannot be corrupted.

MS-ACCESS is therefore used for its fast execution speed and also due to its fast connectivity.

Importance of database:

Growth in the usage of Computers in Business and Industrial sector initiated development of modern Database Software. Database software's offers a number of potential advantages over traditional file-processing system; some of them are as follows:

Program-Data Independence

The separation of data descriptions (metadata) from the application programs that use the data is called data-independence. With the database approach, data descriptions are stored in a central location called repository. This property of the database systems allows an organization's data to change and evolve without changing the application programs that process that data.

Minimal Data-Redundancy

The design goal with database approach is that previously separate and redundant data files are integrated into a single, logical structure. Each primary fact is recorded in only one place in the database. The database approach does not eliminate redundancy entirely, but it allows the designers to carefully control the type and amount of redundancy.

Data Consistency

By controlling data redundancy, we greatly reduce the opportunities for inconsistency. In database approach updating data values is greatly simplified when each value is stored in one place only. Finally we avoid the wasted storage space that results from redundant data storage.

Data Sharing

Primary advantage of database approach is sharing of data. A database is designed as a shared resource. Authorized users are granted permission to use the database and each user is provided one or more user views to facilitate this use. A user view is a logical description of some portion of database that is required by the user to perform some task.

Enforcement of Standards

When the database approach is implemented with full management support, the database administration function should be granted single point authority and responsibility of establishing and enforcing data standards. These standards will include naming conventions, data quality standards and uniform procedures for accessing, updating and processing data. The data repository provides database administrators with powerful tools for developing and enforcing such standards.

Reduced Program Maintenance

Stored data must be changed frequently for a variety of reasons: new data item types are added; data formats are changed and so on. In file processing environment, the description of data formats and access methods inevitably result in the need to modify application programs. As a result in the change of data formats and access methods inevitably results in the need to modify application programs. In a database environment, data are more independent of application programs that use them.

Chapter-6 login Forms & Interpretation

Form 1(code view)

LIST OF TAXIS

Public con As ADODB.Connection

Public rs As ADODB.Recordset

Public Sub dno()

rs.MoveFirst

A = 1

Do While Not rs.EOF

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(A, 0) = A

A = A + 1

rs.MoveNext

Loop

End Sub

Public Sub COUNTRECORD()

'Dim DATA As String

rs.Open "SELECT * FROM TAXIDetails", con, adOpenDynamic,
adLockOptimistic

rs.MoveFirst

'DATA = rs.RecordCount

dno

rs.close

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(1, 0) = DATA

End Sub

Public Sub condata()

Set con = New ADODB.Connection

Set rs = New ADODB.Recordset

con.ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.3.51;Persist Security Info=False;Data Source=C:\Pre Paid Taxi Management System\taxi Management System.mdb"

con.Open

End Sub

Public Sub TABLEDESIGN()

MYTABLE.ColWidth(0) = 1000

MYTABLE.ColWidth(1) = 1000

MYTABLE.ColWidth(2) = 1500

MYTABLE.ColWidth(3) = 1800

MYTABLE.ColWidth(4) = 1500

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(0, 0) = "S.NO"

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(0, 1) = "TAXI NO."

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(0, 2) = "TAXI MODEL"

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(0, 3) = "TAXI LOCATION"

MYTABLE.TextMatrix(0, 4) = "NO OF SEAT"

End Sub

Public Sub DISPLAYTRECORDS()

rs.Open "sELECT * from taxidetails", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

Set MYTABLE.DataSource = rs

rs.close

End Sub

Private Sub close_Click()

Me.Hide

Form6.Show

Form6.WindowState = 2

End Sub

Private Sub Form_Load()

condata

DISPLAYTRECORDS

TABLEDESIGN

COUNTRECORD

End Sub

FORM1 (Execution view)

INTERPRETATION

It may help the employee to keep a track of available taxis and their locations, so that he can select which taxi he can use for a particular booking. It also displays the number of seats in a particular taxi.

FORM 2(code view)

ROUTE CHART

```
Public con As ADODB.Connection
```

```
Public rs As ADODB.Recordset
```

```
Public Sub condata()
```

```
Set con = New ADODB.Connection
```

```
Set rs = New ADODB.Recordset
```

```
con.ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.3.51;Persist Security  
Info=False;Data Source=C:\Pre Paid Taxi Management System\taxi Management  
System.mdb"
```

```
con.Open
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub routeno()
```

```
rs.Open " select * from route", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
A = 0
```

```
Else
```

```
rs.MoveFirst
```

```
Do While Not rs.EOF
```

```
If rs!rno > A Then
```

```
A = rs!rno
```

End If

rs.MoveNext

Loop

End If

rs.close

A = A + 1

Text1.Text = A

End Sub

Public Sub addnewrecord()

rs.Open " route", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

rs.AddNew

rs!rno = Text1.Text

rs!Source = Text2.Text

rs!Destination = Text3.Text

rs!distance = Text4.Text

End Sub

Private Sub clearsearch_Click()

End Sub

Private Sub Command1_Click()

```
addnewrecord
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command10_Click()
```

```
Me.Hide
```

```
Form6.Show
```

```
Form6.WindowState = 2
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command11_Click()
```

```
Dim s As Boolean
```

```
rs.Open "select * from route where rno = " & Val(Text9.Text) & " ", con,  
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
s = False
```

```
MsgBox "There is no record"
```

```
rs.close
```

```
Else
```

```
Text10.Text = rs!Destination
```

```
Text11.Text = rs!Source
```

```
Text12.Text = rs!distance
```

```
s = True
```

```
A = MsgBox("Do you want to modify the record , press ok button", vbOKCancel,  
"To Modify the record")
```

```
If s = True And A = vbOK Then
```

```
Text10.Text = ""
```

```
Text11.Text = ""
```

```
Text12.Text = ""
```

```
Text10.SetFocus
```

```
MsgBox "click on modify button to modify the record"
```

```
End If
```

```
End If
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command12_Click()
```

```
Text9.Text = ""
```

```
Text10.Text = ""
```

```
Text11.Text = ""
```

```
Text12.Text = ""
```

```
Text9.SetFocus
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command13_Click()
rs!Source = Text10.Text
rs!Destination = Text11.Text
rs!distance = Text12.Text
rs.Update
MsgBox "Record is updated successfully"
rs.close

End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command14_Click()
rs.Open "delete from route where rno = " & Val(Text14.Text) & " ", con,
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
MsgBox "Record is deleted "
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command16_Click()
rs.Open "select * from route where rno = " & Val(Text14.Text) & " ", con,
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
If rs.EOF = True Then
s = False
MsgBox "There is no record"
```

```
Else
Text10.Text = rs!Source
Text11.Text = rs!Destination
Text12.Text = rs!distance
s = True
Command17.Visible = True
MsgBox "click on delete button to modify the record"
End If
rs.close
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command4_Click()
Me.Hide
Form6.Show
Form6.WindowState = 2
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command5_Click()
rs.Update
MsgBox "Record is Saved :"
rs.close

End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command6_Click()
```

```
Text1.Text = ""
```

```
Text2.Text = ""
```

```
Text3.Text = ""
```

```
Text4.Text = ""
```

```
routeno
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command7_Click()
```

```
Text5.Text = ""
```

```
Text6.Text = ""
```

```
Text7.Text = ""
```

```
Text8.Text = ""
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command8_Click()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from route where rno = " & Val(Text5.Text) & " ", con,  
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
MsgBox "There is no record"
```

```
Else
```

```
Text7.Text = rs!Source
```

```
Text6.Text = rs!Destination
```

```
Text8.Text = rs!distance
```

```
End If
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command9_Click()
```

```
Me.Hide
```

```
Form6.Show
```

```
Form6.WindowState = 2
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Form_Load()
```

```
condata
```

```
routeno
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub TabStrip1_Click()
```

```
If TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 1 Then
```

```
Frame1(0).Visible = True
```

```
Frame2.Visible = False
```

```
Frame4.Visible = False
Frame3.Visible = False
'Frame2.Visible = False
ElseIf TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 2 Then
Frame2.Visible = True
Frame1(0).Visible = False
Frame4.Visible = False
Frame3.Visible = False
'Text8.SetFocus
'Frame1(2).Visible = False
'Frame1(3).Visible = False
ElseIf TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 3 Then
Frame3.Visible = True
Frame2.Visible = False
Frame4.Visible = False
Frame1(0).Visible = False
'Text12.SetFocus
ElseIf TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 4 Then
Frame4.Visible = True
Frame2.Visible = False
Frame1(0).Visible = False
Frame3.Visible = False
End If
```

End Sub

FORM2(Execution view)

Interpretation

It enables to add a new route to the route list. It helps to maintain the records where the customer has to board the taxi and where it has to escort him.

Interpretation

A particular route can be searched, that is all its details can be accessed simply by filling in the route number and click on the search option.

You can also clear previous record and search for another route number.

ROUTE CHART

Add New Route Search Modify Delete

Modify

Route No	<input type="text" value="9"/>
Source	<input type="text" value="trinagar"/>
Destination	<input type="text" value="azadpur"/>
Distance	<input type="text" value="24"/>

Search Record Modify clear

Taxi Management System [X]

Record is updated successfully

OK

Interpretation

It enables to change or modify the details which have already been added into the record.

FORM 3(code view)

EMPLOYEE DETAILS

Public con As ADODB.Connection

Public rs As ADODB.Recordset

Public Sub increment()

rs.Open "select * from employee", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

If rs.EOF = True Then

A = 0

Else

rs.MoveFirst

Do While Not rs.EOF

If rs!eno > A Then

A = rs!eno

End If

rs.MoveNext

Loop

End If

A = A + 1

Text1.Text = A

rs.close

End Sub

Public Sub benable()

Command1.Enabled = False

Command2.Enabled = False

Command6.Enabled = True

Command7.Enabled = True

End Sub

Public Sub MODIFY()

rs.Open "select * from employee where eno= " & Val(Text1.Text) & " ", con,
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

If rs.EOF = True Then

MsgBox " There is no record"

Else

Text2.Text = rs!eName

Text3.Text = rs!address

dayCombo.Text = Day(rs!dateofjoin)

monCombo2.Text = Month(rs!dateofjoin)

yeartxt.Text = Year(rs!dateofjoin)

Text4.Text = rs!contactno

End If

Text2.Text = ""

Text3.Text = ""

Text4.Text = ""

```
dayCombo.Text = "Day"
```

```
monCombo2.Text = "Month"
```

```
Text2.SetFocus
```

```
MsgBox " click to update button for changing the record"
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub del()
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub condata()
```

```
Set con = New ADODB.Connection
```

```
Set rs = New ADODB.Recordset
```

```
con.ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.3.51;Persist Security  
Info=False;Data Source=C:\Pre Paid Taxi Management System\taxi Management  
System.mdb"
```

```
con.Open
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub addrecord()
```

```
rs.Open "employee", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
rs.AddNew
```

```
rs!eName = Text2.Text
```

```
rs!eno = Val(Text1.Text)
```

```
rs!address = Text3.Text
```

```
rs!dateofjoin = CDate(monCombo2.Text + "-" + dayCombo.Text + "-" +  
yeartxt.Text)
```

```
rs!contactno = Text4.Text
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command1_Click()
```

```
addrecord
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command2_Click()
```

```
rs.Update
```

```
MsgBox "Record is saved "
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command3_Click()
```

```
Text1.Text = ""
```

```
Text2.Text = ""
```

```
Text3.Text = ""
```

```
Text4.Text = ""
```

```
dayCombo.Text = "Day"
```

```
monCombo2.Text = "Month"
```

```
Text2.SetFocus
```

```
increment
```

```
Command1.Enabled = True
```

```
Command2.Enabled = True
```

```
Command6.Enabled = False
```

```
Command7.Enabled = False
```

```
Command8.Enabled = False
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command4_Click()
```

```
Me.Hide
```

```
Form6.Show
```

```
Form6.WindowState = 2
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command5_Click()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from employee where eno= " & Val(Text1.Text) & " ", con,  
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
MsgBox " There is no record"
```

```
Else
```

```
Text2.Text = rs!eName
```

```
Text3.Text = rs!address
dayCombo.Text = Day(rs!dateofjoin)
monCombo2.Text = Month(rs!dateofjoin)
yeartxt.Text = Year(rs!dateofjoin)
Text4.Text = rs!contactno
End If
rs.close
benable
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command6_Click()
MODIFY
Command8.Enabled = True
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command7_Click()
rs.Open "delete from employee where eno = " & Val(Text1.Text) & " ", con,
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
MsgBox "Record is deleted "
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command8_Click()
rs!eName = Text2.Text
```

```
'rs!eno = Val(Text1.Text)
```

```
rs!address = Text3.Text
```

```
rs!dateofjoin = CDate(monCombo2.Text + "-" + dayCombo.Text + "-" +  
yeartxt.Text)
```

```
rs!contactno = Text4.Text
```

```
MsgBox "Please click on save button "
```

```
Call Command2_Click
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Form_Load()
```

```
yeartxt.Text = DatePart("yyyy", Date)
```

```
condata
```

```
increment
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub UpDown1_DownClick()
```

```
yeartxt.Text = Val(yeartxt) - 1
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub UpDown1_UpClick()
```

```
yeartxt.Text = Val(yeartxt) + 1
```

```
End Sub
```

FORM 3(Execution view)

TAXI MANAGEMENT SYSTEM - [Employee Details]

TAXI DETAILS ROUTE EMPLOYEE BOOKING HELP EXIT

Employee Details

Employee No:

Employee Name:

Address:

Date Of Joining:

Contact No:

Taxi Management System

Record is saved

start RealPlay... Structure... Tata Pho... retros 2 Micro... 2 Visual... Microsoft... 3:23 PM

INTERPRETATION

It keeps a record of all the employees who are working in this firm. The user can add new employees by filling in the details that is employee number, name, address, and the date of joining. This helps to maintain the employee records.

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "TAXI MANAGEMENT SYSTEM - [Employee Details]". The window has a menu bar with "TAXI DETAILS", "ROUTE", "EMPLOYEE", "BOOKING", "HELP", and "EXIT". The main content area is titled "Employee Details" and contains the following form fields:

- Employee No:
- Employee Name:
- Address:
- Date Of Joining:
- Contact No:

Below the form are three buttons: "Search", "Clear", and "Close". The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the Start button and several open applications: RealPlay..., Structure..., Tata Pho..., retros, 2 Micro..., 2 Visual..., and Microsoft... The system clock shows 3:25 PM.

INTERPRETATION

Through this the user can extract all the details of the employees by filling in employee number. All the details regarding that employee will be disclosed their , that is the date of joining his name and address.

Interpretations

Through this we can modify the employee record, if any change had occur, or if any employee has resigned himself , then on his employee number we can take another employee by just clicking on the modify button and then on the update button. The particular record will be saved.

Interpretations

Through this user can permanently delete the record of the employees in case he or she has resigned or quit the job without any substitutes employee.

FORM 4 (Code view)

BOOKING OF TAXI

Public con As ADODB.Connection

Public rs As ADODB.Recordset

Public rs2 As ADODB.Recordset

Public Sub datacon()

Set con = New ADODB.Connection

Set rs = New ADODB.Recordset

Set rs2 = New ADODB.Recordset

con.ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.3.51;Persist Security Info=False;Data Source=C:\Pre Paid Taxi Management System\taxi Management System.mdb"

con.Open

End Sub

Public Sub ROUTE()

rs.Open "select * from route ", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

If Not rs.EOF = True Then

rs.MoveFirst

Do While Not rs.EOF

Combo1.AddItem (rs!rno)

rs.MoveNext

Loop

Else

```
Combo1.AddItem ("there is no route")
```

```
End If
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub driver()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from employee ", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If Not rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
rs.MoveFirst
```

```
Do While Not rs.EOF
```

```
Combo2.AddItem (rs!eno)
```

```
rs.MoveNext
```

```
Loop
```

```
Else
```

```
Combo2.AddItem ("there is no route")
```

```
End If
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub disemp()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from employee where eno = " & Val(Combo2.Text) & " ", con,  
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If Not rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
rs.MoveFirst
```

```
Do While Not rs.EOF
```

```
Text10.Text = rs!eName
```

```
Text11.Text = rs!contactno
```

```
rs.MoveNext
```

```
Loop
```

```
Else
```

```
MsgBox "there is no driver "
```

```
End If
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub disroute()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from route where rno = " & Val(Combo1.Text) & " ", con,  
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If Not rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
rs.MoveFirst
```

```
Do While Not rs.EOF
```

```
Text5.Text = rs!Source
```

```
Text6.Text = rs!Destination
```

```
Text7.Text = rs!distance
```

```
rs.MoveNext
```

```
Loop
```

```
Else
```

```
MsgBox "there is no route"
```

End If

rs.close

End Sub

Private Sub Command1_Click()

disroute

End Sub

Private Sub Command2_Click()

Text9.Text = Val(Text7.Text) * Val(Text8.Text)

End Sub

Private Sub Command3_Click()

Text5.Text = ""

Text6.Text = ""

Text7.Text = ""

Text8.Text = ""

Text9.Text = ""

Combo1.Text = "Select Route No"

End Sub

Private Sub Command4_Click()

disemp

End Sub

Private Sub Command5_Click()

Text10.Text = ""

Text11.Text = ""

Combo2.Text = "Driver No"

End Sub

Public Sub BOOKING()

rs.Open "booking", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

rs.AddNew

rs!bno = Val(Text2.Text)

rs!CName = Text1.Text

rs!Cinfo = Text3.Text

rs!CNo = Text4.Text

rs!Source = Text5.Text

rs!Destination = Text6.Text

rs!distance = Text7.Text

rs!BookingDate = CDate(Date)

rs!eName = Text10.Text

rs!eCont = Text11.Text

End Sub

Private Sub Command6_Click()

```
rs.Open "booking", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
rs.AddNew
```

```
rs!bno = Val(Text2.Text)
```

```
rs!CName = Text1.Text
```

```
rs!Cinfo = Text3.Text
```

```
rs!CNo = Text4.Text
```

```
rs!Rsou = Text5.Text
```

```
rs!Rdes = Text6.Text
```

```
rs!rDist = Text7.Text
```

```
rs!BookingDate = CDate(Date)
```

```
rs!eName = Text10.Text
```

```
rs!eCont = Text11.Text
```

```
rs!bill = Val(Text9.Text)
```

```
'booking
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command7_Click()
```

```
rs.Update
```

```
MsgBox "Record is saved sucessfully"
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command8_Click()
```

Command3_Click

Command5_Click

Text1.Text = ""

Text2.Text = ""

Text3.Text = ""

Text4.Text = ""

Text1.SetFocus

End Sub

Private Sub Command9_Click()

Me.Hide

Form6.Show

Form6.WindowState = 2

End Sub

Private Sub Form_Load()

datacon

ROUTE

driver

End Sub

FORM 4 (Execution view)

The screenshot displays a Windows application window titled "TAXI MANAGEMENT SYSTEM - [Booking of Taxi]". The menu bar includes "TAXI DETAILS", "ROUTE", "EMPLOYEE", "BOOKING", "HELP", and "EXIT". The main form is titled "BOOKING OF TAXI" and is divided into three sections: "CUSTOMER DETAILS", "ROUTE INFORMATION", and "Driver Details".

CUSTOMER DETAILS

Customer Name	JAIPAL	Booking No	10
Customer information	MANAGER	Contact No	89685525

ROUTE INFORMATION

3	Source	dwarka	Distance
Display Route	Destination	ISBT	55
Charges	12	Bill	660
Per / KM		Calculate	Clear

Driver Details

2	Driver Name	dheeraj	Contact No	324523
Display Details			Clear	

Buttons at the bottom of the form: Booking, Save, Clear, Close.

A modal dialog box titled "Taxi Management System" is overlaid on the form, displaying the message "Record is saved sucessfully" and an "OK" button.

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the start button and several open applications: RealPlay..., Structure..., Tata Pho..., retros, 2 Micro..., 2 Visual..., and Microsoft... The system clock shows 4:02 PM.

Microsoft Access - Table Tools - Datasheet

Security Warning: Certain content in the database has been disabled. Options...

All Access Objects - Tables

- booking
- Employee
- route
- taxidetails

cname	cno	cinfo	rsou	rdes	rdist	ename	econt
ram kumar	1237462364	narela	rani nagar	new delhi	78	jasbir	9968483079
gaurav	996558525	adarsh	jahangirpuri m	dhaula kuan	26	shyam	99714125255
radhe	988995522	officer	dwarka	ISBT	55	dheeraj	32452335
sudhir	948555587	student	narela	Dwarka	70	geeta	98272173171
deepak	999995585	mahendd	jahangirpuri m	dhaula kuan	26	shyam	99714125255
maresh	989696585	ndpl	shahbad dairy	rajghat	53	dheeraj	32452335
JAIPAL	89685525	MANAGER	dwarka	ISBT	55	dheeraj	32452335

Record: 7 of 7 | No Filter | Search

Datasheet View | Caps Lock | Num Lock

Windows Taskbar: start, RealPlay..., Structure..., Tata Pho..., retros, 2 Micro..., 2 Visual..., Microsoft..., 4:06 PM

INTERPRETATION

Through this the user can book the taxi by entering the customer details, route number and the charges to be applied per K.M. This will calculate expense to be borne by the customer and will also save the booking in to the records.

FORM 5(Code view)

BOOKING DETAILS

```
Public con As ADODB.Connection
```

```
Public rs As ADODB.Recordset
```

```
Public Sub condata()
```

```
Set con = New ADODB.Connection
```

```
Set rs = New ADODB.Recordset
```

```
con.ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.3.51;Persist Security  
Info=False;Data Source=C:\Pre Paid Taxi Management System\taxi Management  
System.mdb"
```

```
con.Open
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub delrecord(no As Integer)
```

```
Dim data As Integer
```

```
data = tabledata.TextMatrix(no, 0)
```

```
'Text1.Text = data
```

```
rs.Open "delete from booking where bno = " & data & "'", con, adOpenDynamic,  
adLockOptimistic
```

```
MsgBox "Record is deleted "
```

```
tabledata.RemoveItem (no)
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub record(rno As Integer)
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 0) = rs!bno
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 1) = rs!BookingDate
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 2) = rs!CName
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 3) = rs!Cinfo
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 4) = rs!CNo
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 5) = rs!Rsou
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 6) = rs!Rdes
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 7) = rs!rDist
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 8) = rs!bill
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 9) = rs!eName
```

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(rno, 10) = rs!eCont
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub displayrecord()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from booking", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
MsgBox "There is no record"
```

```
Else
```

```
rs.MoveFirst
```

```
A = 1
```

```
Do While Not rs.EOF
```

```
record (A)
```

```
A = A + 1
```

```
rs.MoveNext
```

```
Loop
```

End If

rs.close

End Sub

Public Sub tablecolsize()

tabledata.ColWidth(0) = 1000

tabledata.ColWidth(1) = 1200

tabledata.ColWidth(2) = 1500

tabledata.ColWidth(3) = 1800

tabledata.ColWidth(4) = 1900

tabledata.ColWidth(5) = 1100

tabledata.ColWidth(6) = 1700

tabledata.ColWidth(7) = 1000

tabledata.ColWidth(8) = 800

tabledata.ColWidth(9) = 1500

tabledata.ColWidth(10) = 1500

End Sub

Public Sub display()

tablecolsize

tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 0) = "Booking No"

tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 1) = "Booking Date"

tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 2) = "Customer Name"

tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 3) = "Customer Address"

tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 4) = "Customer Contact No"

```
tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 5) = "Route From"  
tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 6) = "Route Destination"  
tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 7) = "Distance"  
tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 8) = "Bill"  
tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 9) = "Driver Name"  
tabledata.TextMatrix(0, 10) = "Driver Contact No"
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command1_Click()
```

```
displayrecord
```

```
"Text1.Text = tabledata.RowSel
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command2_Click()
```

```
Dim no As Integer
```

```
no = tabledata.RowSel
```

```
delrecord (no)
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command3_Click()
```

```
tabledata.Clear
```

```
display
```

End Sub

Private Sub Command4_Click()

Me.Hide

Form6.Show

Form6.WindowState = 2

End Sub

Private Sub Form_Load()

display

condata

End Sub

FORM 6 (Code view)

TAXI DETAILS

```
Public con As ADODB.Connection
```

```
Public rs As ADODB.Recordset
```

```
Public Sub addrecord()
```

```
rs.Open "Select * from taxidetails", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
rs.AddNew
```

```
rs!taxino = Val(Text1.Text)
```

```
rs!taximodel = Text2.Text
```

```
rs!location = Text3.Text
```

```
rs!noseat = Val(Text4.Text)
```

```
rs.Update
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub deleterecord()
```

```
Dim s As Boolean
```

```
s = True
```

```
rs.Open "select * from taxidetails where taxino = " & Val(Text16.Text) & " ",  
con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
MsgBox "There is no record"
```

```
s = False
```

Else

Text15.Text = rs!taximodel

Text14.Text = rs!location

Text13.Text = rs!noseat

s = True

End If

rs.close

A = MsgBox("Do you want to delete the record ,press ok button ", vbOKCancel,
"To Delete the record")

If s = True And A = vbOK Then

rs.Open "Delete * from taxidetails where taxino =" & Val(Text16.Text) & "", con,
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

If rs.ActiveCommand = True Then

MsgBox "This record is deleted"

Else

MsgBox "This record is not deleted"

End If

rs.Close

End If

End Sub

Public Sub condata()

Set con = New ADODB.Connection

Set rs = New ADODB.Recordset

```
con.ConnectionString = "Provider=Microsoft.Jet.OLEDB.3.51;Persist Security Info=False;Data Source=C:\Pre Paid Taxi Management System\taxi Management System.mdb"
```

```
con.Open
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command1_Click()
```

```
addrecord
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command10_Click()
```

```
Me.Hide
```

```
Form6.Show
```

```
Form6.WindowState = 2
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command11_Click()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from taxidetails where taxino = " & Val(Text12.Text) & " ",  
con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
MsgBox "There is no record"
```

```
Else
```

```
Text11.Text = rs!taximodel
```

```
Text10.Text = rs!location
```

```
Text9.Text = rs!noseat
```

```
End If
```

```
i = MsgBox("Do you want to modify this record , click ok button ", vbOKCancel,  
"To Modify record ")
```

```
If i = vbOK Then
```

```
Text11.Text = ""
```

```
Text10.Text = ""
```

```
Text9.Text = ""
```

```
MsgBox "Click update button"
```

```
Command13.Enabled = True
```

```
Else
```

```
MsgBox "There is no record "
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End If
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command12_Click()
```

```
Text16.Text = ""
```

```
Text15.Text = ""
```

```
Text14.Text = ""
```

```
Text13.Text = ""
```

```
Text16.SetFocus
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command13_Click()
```

```
rs!taxino = Val(Text12.Text)
```

```
rs!taximodel = Text11.Text
```

```
rs!location = Text10.Text
```

```
rs!noseat = Val(Text9.Text)
```

```
rs.Update
```

```
MsgBox "Record is updated "
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command14_Click()
```

```
deleterecord
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command2_Click()
```

```
MsgBox "Record is Saved"
```

```
rs.close
```

```
End Sub
```

```
Public Sub increno()
```

```
rs.Open "select * from taxidetails", con, adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic
```

```
If rs.EOF = True Then
```

```
A = 0
Else
rs.MoveFirst
Do While Not rs.EOF
If Val(rs!taxino) > A Then
A = rs!taxino
End If
rs.MoveNext
Loop
End If
A = A + 1
Text1.Text = A
rs.close
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command3_Click()
Text1.Text = ""
Text2.Text = ""
Text3.Text = ""
Text4.Text = ""
increno
Text2.SetFocus
```

End Sub

Public Sub searchrecord()

rs.Open "select * from taxidetails where taxino = " & Val(Text8.Text) & " ", con,
adOpenDynamic, adLockOptimistic

If rs.EOF = True Then

MsgBox "There is no record"

Else

Text7.Text = rs!taximodel

Text6.Text = rs!location

Text5.Text = rs!noseat

End If

rs.close

End Sub

Private Sub Command4_Click()

Me.Hide

Form6.Show

Form6.WindowState = 2

End Sub

Private Sub Command5_Click()

Me.Hide

```
Form6.Show
Form6.WindowState = 2
Frame1(0).Visible = True
Frame2.Visible = False
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command6_Click()
Text8.Text = ""
Text7.Text = ""
Text6.Text = ""
Text5.Text = ""
Text8.SetFocus
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command7_Click()
Frame1(0).Visible = True
Frame3.Visible = False
Me.Hide
Form6.Show
Form6.WindowState = 2
End Sub
```

```
Private Sub Command8_Click()
```

searchrecord

End Sub

Private Sub Command9_Click()

Text12.Text = ""

Text11.Text = ""

Text10.Text = ""

Text9.Text = ""

Text12.SetFocus

End Sub

Private Sub Form_Load()

condata

increno

End Sub

Private Sub TabStrip1_Click()

If TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 1 Then

Frame1(0).Visible = True

Frame2.Visible = False

Frame4.Visible = False

Frame3.Visible = False

Frame2.Visible = False

```
ElseIf TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 2 Then
    Frame2.Visible = True
    Frame1(0).Visible = False
    Frame4.Visible = False
    Frame3.Visible = False
    Text8.SetFocus
    Frame1(2).Visible = False
    Frame1(3).Visible = False
ElseIf TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 3 Then
    Frame3.Visible = True
    Frame2.Visible = False
    Frame4.Visible = False
    Frame1(0).Visible = False
    Text12.SetFocus
ElseIf TabStrip1.SelectedItem.Index = 4 Then
    Frame4.Visible = True
    Frame2.Visible = False
    Frame1(0).Visible = False
    Frame3.Visible = False
End If
End Sub
```


INTERPRETATION

Through this form the user can add a new taxi by filling the details in their specified columns. This helps to maintain the records in case new taxis are bought by the firm.

INTERPRETATION

Through this form the user can search a taxi by entering the taxi number. It displays the locations and number of seats in the taxi.

Interpretations

Through we can modify the details of the taxi. By clicking in the modify button and then on the update button. This will save the new details of the taxi.

Interpretations

Through this form the user can delete the taxi model from the list of taxis by filling the taxi number and clicking on the delete button.

CONCLUSIONS

This project is about the designing Prepaid taxi management database system using M S Access, and Visual Basic 6.0. This project presents an investigative view of presenting the taxi management system including the history of taxis. Present system of taxi management system is having some shortcoming on which we have tried to work on that to eliminate the disadvantages. We have made a database for customers and taxis and connected these two tables from the custom made data entry form built in Visual Basic 6.0. There are options for new entry which will be stored in M S Access database and retrieved from database in future. This project was a small attempt to make the railway reservation database system using M S Access, and Visual Basic 6.0. We have talked with some of the employees of delhi cab service about the features and shortcoming of present taxi management system after the research with the associated people and other sources we were able to found out some of the major facts regarding the taxi management system and tried to eliminate the shortcoming of system.

In the last we conclude that Nepaln taxi is having a strong IT Infrastructure and a well-equipped taxi management system but there is some shortcoming in the system on which we have tried to work on it and successfully completed our project.

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